

MOSAIC STYLE IN A MAJESTIC PAINTING

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Annotation: This article describes in detail about the style of mosaic in mahogany painting, the style of mosaic work, stained glass, one of the most beautiful and colorful types of mahogany decorative art, the decorative art of mahogany painting.

Keywords: majestic painting, decorative arts, stained glass, mosaic style, composition.

Introduction:

Works using new types of materials in contemporary architecture do not leave many viewers indifferent. Including a whole composition with an artistic image, its content and essence is distinguished by the modernity of the development technique and aesthetic perfection. According to the strategy of subconscious development, humanity strives for the beauty of nature and again for naturalness.

He delights in seeing beautiful structures. Modern architecture in a majestic painting covers new types of objects in several styles, such as mosaics, stained glass, and other wall paintings. The goal is to decorate the interior and exterior of the building with a beautiful aesthetic taste and show what the building is for.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The language of the composition is simple and clear, has an understandable artistry. The lines and silhouettes are expressive, and the splashes of color are decorative. When choosing a building, clarifying the subject includes working on the foresight, working on the foresight in color, looking for various options in tone, finding a composition solution, paying attention to the center, paying attention to the color of the composition, working on details, etc.

The composition can be in large foyers, vestibules, museum halls, library halls, as well as socially important buildings in the interior of the building. In some buildings, it is also used as a household decoration. In addition to a number of styles of wall mosaics and stained-glass sgraffito, the types of modern architecture are new types of modern architecture, including the type of tapestry art.

Results: The type of mosaic made of smalta stones, which was widely used in those times, is still used today. Smalta is an artificial colored stone. The ancient Egyptians colored Smalta stone using metal oxides. For many years, it has been used as a decorative stone in furniture and household items. The main element of the Roman mosaic is a small cube-shaped colored stone or smalta, which was called a module.

Small modular mosaics are used in applied art as a decorative decoration for decorating household items. But the main use of mosaic is in monumental art. Mosaic is one of the oldest forms of architectural decoration. Even now, mosaic is developing artistically without losing its value, and new techniques, technologies, and methods are being created. Later, the Florentine mosaic appeared.

Although the style of mosaic work is more difficult, the bright color of mosaic stones, color stability, and long-term durability have attracted great interest among artists. Mosaic can be stored for a hundred years. There are two commonly used types of mosaic, Roman mosaic and Florentine mosaic. Roman mosaic is made by crushing colored smalta stones.

Discussion:

Florentine mosaic is a composition of large natural thin marble stones of various colors and shades. The method of execution of these two types is quite different from each other. There is also a unique mosaic in Uzbekistan, the buildings are decorated with various patterns and inscriptions using the art of pottery. For example, we can see colored tiles made in pottery in the buildings of Bukhara and Khiva.

In the Italian city of Florence in the 16th century, another form of mosaic technique spread. Based on a picture or a monumental template, it was started to be picked from larger pieces of colored marble stone. Such a mosaic was called a Florentine mosaic. There are also types of covering one side of the brick with colored glaze.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that as the current modern architecture develops, the need for abstract works is increasing, and the attention to realistic works is decreasing. At such a time, we should learn from teachers based on the directions of public education, learn artistic solutions in composition and majestic painting styles such as fresco, mosaic, stained glass, and sgraffito and deliver them to the next generation.

Stained glass is one of the most beautiful and colorful types of decorative art. It is made in place of the window of architectural buildings and is widely used in decorating the interior and exterior of the building. It has a strong decorative finish. The power of stained glass is stained glass. An example of this is the historical development of stained glass as an art form and the fact that modern stained glass is practiced in many countries.

References:

1. "Art" magazine of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan. 2019.
2. Rustam Hudaiberganov. A magnificent decorative art composition. 2004.
3. N. Normatov. "Road to the land of colors". -T.: "Publisher", 2013.
4. Khudaiberganov R.A. "Fundamentals of color science". - T.: G. Gulam. 2006.
5. Babadzhanova G.I. Principles of interaction of monumental art and architecture. "Architecture and construction of Uzbekistan". 2004.
6. Winner A.V. "Materials and techniques of monumental-decorative painting". -M.: "Art", 2001.